

Implementation and Impact of Green Human Resource Management Practices for Employee Pro-Environmental Behavior in Tourist Hotels in Tanzania

Rutasimbala G. Raymond [0009-0002-5407-2192]

Supervisor: S D Lukea Bhiwajee [0000-0002-4049-2594]

University of Technology, Mauritius, La Tour Koenig, Pointe Aux Sables, Port Louis

rutasimbala.raymond@umail.utm.ac.mu, sbhiwajee@utm.ac.mu

1 Background Information of the Study

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is defined as “policies and practices of human resource management used in the organisation to influence pro-environmental behaviour among employees to ensure environmental management and organisational competitiveness” [4, 6]. The concerns for environmental management pressured organisations to integrate human resource management functions with environmental issues [17, 20-21]. This is because climate change, global warming and environmental pollution attract global attention to society, governments and organisations [10, 19, 26]. The concern for environmental management gained momentum and emerged as a global agenda in the past few decades [3, 13, 22, 35]. It also gained impetus in the 21st century [3] when organisations increased their sense of pressure to incorporate human resource management functions with environmental management issues [8, 28, 30]. In 2012, the global temperature was approximately 0.85°C, and now it has increased to approximately an average temperature of 1.5°C [21]. This influences national and international organisations to participate and include environmental management issues in their policies, strategies and practices [11, 17, 29]. As international strategies, sustainable development goals 13, 14 and 15 were introduced by the United Nations (UN) as among the agenda 2030 sustainable development goals (SDGs) to ensure global participation in environmental management [7]. Furthermore, the United Nations (UN) has taken steps to ensure environmental management through resolutions and agreements like the Kyoto Protocol of 1997, the Paris Agreement of 2015 and the Glasgow Climate Pact of 2021 [25, 38]. African countries have taken steps in environmental management to adopt a sustainable environment and blue economy strategy [12, 32]. Organisations have been adopting different mechanisms for environmental management, such as green marketing, green accounting and green management [38]. Currently, organisations have expanded their horizon to implement and integrate human resource management functions with environmental management policies. This is termed green human resource management practices, abbreviated as GHRM practices. GHRM practices are implemented through recruitment and selection, training and development, rewards, performance management and employee relations. The implementation of GHRM practices focuses on

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generating employee pro-environmental behaviour that leads to environmental sustainability [34, 36]. Implementing GHRM practices allows the integration of human resource management functions like training, motivation and performance evaluation with environmental management aspects [6, 38]. This draws attention and attracts practitioners and scholars to study the implementation and impacts of green human resource management practices. [5, 9, 16, 31, 38, 41, 43], commented that theoretical studies on the implementation and impacts of GHRM practices have been conducted in developed countries like Europe, Asian countries and the US but are less considerable in developing countries like Tanzania. [3, 24, 28, 44], commented that the implementation of GHRM practices in developing countries, including Tanzania, is still in the infant stage from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a study to investigate the implementation and impacts of green human resource management (GHRM) practices on employees' pro-environmental behaviour, particularly in tourist hotels in Tanzania, to bridge the gap in the deficiency of the existing literature.

2 Statement of the Problem

Global concerns for environmental management force organisations to integrate human resource management functions with environmental issues [18, 21]. This is because green human resource management practices increase waste management skills, train employees on energy saving and influence employee green behaviour [1]. Moreover, green human resource management (GHRM) practices cultivate employee green knowledge, pro-environmental behaviour and employee green psychology in the organisation. However, environmental problems affect society, governments and organisations [6, 19]. Environmental problems like climate change, global warming, and environmental pollution attract global attention from society, governments, and organisations [10, 14, 26, 36]. For example, in 2012, the global temperature was approximately 0.85°C, and now it has increased to approximately an average temperature of 1.5°C [21]. This influences organisations to participate and include environmental management issues in their policies, strategies and practices. As International strategies, sustainable development goals 13, 14 and 15 were introduced to ensure global participation in environmental management [7]. Furthermore, various mechanisms have been made by the United Nations to show efforts for environmental management, such as the Kyoto Protocol of 1997, the Paris Agreement of 2015 and the Glasgow climate pact of 2021 [26, 37, 38]. African countries, through the umbrella of the African Union, have taken steps for environmental management, such as a sustainable environment and blue economy [30]. Organisations have been adopting different mechanisms for environmental management, such as green marketing, green accounting and green management [38]. Currently, organisations have expanded their horizon to integrate environmental management policies with human resource management functions. All these efforts force organisations to implement GHRM practices in their organisation to ensure organisational competitiveness and sustainability. [24, 44] explained that in developing countries, GHRM practices are a new concept. In this regard, the implementation of GHRM practices is questionable in many organisations, particularly in tourist hotels in Tanzania. Amrutha and Geetha [5] explained

that in the European context, trade unions have a significant influence on environmental management. Therefore, trade unions can act as barriers to implementing GHRM practices if the country has rigid laws. The social exchange theory explains that organisations have to grant opportunity and motivation to employees, particularly through representatives; this will develop a sense of identity that influences pro-environmental behaviour. Furthermore, the literature shows that there is limited literature in developing countries, particularly in Tanzania, which raises this question that needs to be answered. [38], pointed out that the essence of implementing GHRM practices in the organisation is not only to change production, products or services but also to change organisational culture by embedding deep employee value in environment management. [40], explain that the impacts of implementing GHRM practices include a commitment from employees, high production, cost reduction and employee retention, which results in environmental performance. This study is important to be conducted in developing countries, specifically in Tanzania, so as to enrich the existing literature conducted in developing countries, specifically in tourist hotels in Tanzania. In Tanzania, there is no study conducted in tourist hotels regarding to the implementation and impact of GHRM practices for pro-environmental behaviour. This study will be guided by three research questions, namely;

- i. To what extent does implementing green human resource management practices in tourist hotels impact environmental sustainability in Tanzania?
- ii. How do barriers to implementing green human resource management practices in tourist hotels hinder environmental sustainability in Tanzania?

3 Research Methodology

This research will employ an exploratory design, and a qualitative research design will be adopted. Based on a few extant studies [8, 15], the case study design is the most appropriate method to be applied in the study. It allows the exploration of data in which interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) can be used in different cases. Different tourist hotels in Tanzania that stipulate the practice of GHRM in their plans and policies have been chosen as cases. Three regions of Tanzania that have well-known tourist attractions (Dar es Salaam, Arusha, and Zanzibar) (URT, 2022) have been earmarked for this purpose. The study will make use of both primary and secondary data.

Primary data: The study will collect first-hand data directly from the field through interviews and focus group discussions [34, 43]. Relevant employees and HR managers will be requested to take part in the study.

Secondary data will be obtained from literature searches using specific keywords and phrases to tap the most relevant information. Keywords/phrases such as green human resource management, green human resource management practices, green HRM practices, GHRM practices, sustainability of human resource management and environmental sustainability will be used. High-impact factor journals through available electronic databases, including Elsevier, Emerald Insight, Sage Publication, Wiley Online Library, Springer, and Taylor and Francis (online and Routledge will be used for this purpose. The study will also review various documents pertaining to laws,

policies, and regulations and reports from the ILO, UN, UNEP, AU, government and organisations.

Data analysis: Data collected will be analysed qualitatively by using thematic analysis. Suppose required data analysis software like Nvivo or thematic analysis will be applied to aid the analysis process. Prior to data collection, the researcher will seek clearance from the university's ethical committee and also request the required research permit from Tanzanian organisations to conduct the study as appropriate. Ethical consent will also be sought from respondents before collecting data.

4 Description of the Artifact

The artifact of this study is based on the research variable, which is green human resource management GHRM practices. Green human resource management practices include green recruitment and selection, green training and development, green rewards and compensation, green job design and evaluation and green performance management. The implementations of GHRM practices influence environmental sustainability in tourist hotels. Moreover, the implementation of GHRM practices cultivates employees' green behaviours in the organization. Also, GHRM practices encourage and contribute to cultivating employees' green behaviour, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

5 Summary of Work done to Date

The study started in November 2023. An intensive literature review has been done to identify the existing gap. A systematic literature review pertaining to the concept of green human resource management practices concept has been conducted. Keywords identified include “green human resource management”, “green human resource management practices”, “green HRM practices”, “GHRM practices”, “sustainability of human resource management” and “environmental sustainability. Approximately more than 100 sources, including journal articles, book chapters, and conference papers, have been reviewed based on the keywords criteria. Journal articles were searched from research databases or publishing companies like Elsevier, Emerald Insight, Sage publication, Wiley Online Library, Springer and Taylor and Francis (online and Routledge).

6 Contribution of the Study

The study expects to contribute to a wider understanding of the existing literature pertaining to green human resource management practices. The findings of the study will enable organisations to have the best option for the appropriate implementation of GHRM practices for environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the study will enlighten governments on the appropriate policies and regulations to be improved to ensure the effective implementation of GHRM practices for the environment.

7 Research Assurance of Transparency

The research will ensure transparency through impartiality and independence during data collection. The researcher will be grounded by positivism, which allows for neutral and providing relevant and trustworthy information [41]. Furthermore, data will be collected from the organisation in which the researcher has no personal interest. The selection of the organisation will be based on scientific justifications, and the researcher will also ensure validity by conducting a pilot study before the actual data collection process. Furthermore, the researcher will apply for research clearance permits from the University of Technology, Mauritius and relevant authorities from the tourism sector in Tanzania.

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Implementation and Impact of Green Human Resource Management Practices

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Rutasimbala G. Raymond

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